

THE MAIN ARTISTIC AND LITERARY TRENDS OF THE SILVER AGE**Sharafutdinova Marvar Rashidovna**

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Annotation.

The article examines a turning point in the historical development of social and artistic life in Russia, a revision of artistic values, an update of literary techniques, the emergence of new literary trends, a new period in the history of Russian culture called the Silver Age (1890-1920).

Key words: the pinnacle of Russian poetry, prose, a turning point in history, artistic values, literary techniques, literary movements, the Silver Age

The literature of the Silver Age (late 19th – early 20th centuries) was an era of widespread spiritual revival, a flourishing of poetry and philosophy, marked by a search for new artistic forms, profound psychological insight, and a search for God. It modernized the Russian language, combining cultural traditions with innovation, and enriched world art.

The 19th century, and especially its first half, was the pinnacle of Russian poetry. This was its "golden age." Pushkin, Lermontov, Nekrasov, Tyutchev, and Fet lived and worked during this time.

In the second half of the last century, prose dominated Russian literature. No new outstanding poets emerged. At the turn of the 20th century, a "new" poetry emerged.

The early 20th century was a turning point in the development of social and artistic life in Russia. Artistic values were being reconsidered, literary techniques were being updated, and realism continued to evolve.

The theme of Russia's destiny, its spiritual and moral essence, and its historical future became central to the works of writers of various ideological and literary schools. Interest in issues of national character and human nature intensified, but these issues were addressed in different ways. This theme was evident in the works of writers who continued to work in the realistic direction, such as A. I. Kuprin (1870-1938), V. V. Veresayev (1867-1945), I. A. Bunin (1870-1953), M. Gorky (1868-1936), and others.

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Tema sud'by Rossii, yeyo dukhovno-nravstvennoy sushchnosti i istoricheskogo budushchego stanovitsya tsentral'noy v tvorchestve pisateley raznykh ideynykh i literaturnykh napravleniy. Obostryayetsya interes k problemam natsional'nogo kharaktera, prirody cheloveka, no reshayutsya eti problemy po-raznomu. V tvorchestve pisateley, prodolzhayushchikh rabotat' v realisticheskoy napravlenii, takikh kak A. I. Kuprin (1870-1938), V. V. Veresayev (1867-1945), I. A. Bunin (1870-1953), M. Gor'kiy (1868-1936) i dr.

But poetry developed particularly dynamically. A little later, this period would be called the Silver Age of Russian Poetry.

The Silver Age is the name of a period in the history of Russian culture (1890-1920). This new literary and historical era is not only a continuation of traditions but also a rejection of the old, a search for new artistic techniques. The social and civic themes of the Golden Age, which were the foundation of Russian literature, are fading. Poets find interest in the philosophical themes of God, Life, and Death. The Silver Age marked the beginning of Russian modernism and ushered in new literary movements. The main ones are Symbolism, Acmeism, Imagism, and Futurism.

The "Silver Age" of New Poetry:

A. A. Blok, B. L. Pasternak, A. A. Akhmatova,
S. A. Yesenin, V. V. Mayakovsky, A. Bely,
M. I. Tsvetaeva, N. S. Gumilyov, V. Ya. Bryusov.

The poets of the Silver Age were literate, educated people. They sought to draw on the best of realism, romanticism, and classicism, developing their traditions, and moving forward. They were meticulous with words, because they expressed, above all, the poet's soul.

The "Golden Age" of Russian literature was replaced by a new one—the "Silver Age." It became an era of new poetic trends, creating communities of poets, each with their own unique style.

Who invented the "Silver Age"?

The tradition of naming cultural eras after the properties of metals dates back to antiquity. It's unclear who exactly coined the term "Silver Age." According to one theory, the period was named after the "Golden Age" of Russian literature; another suggests it was taken from Anna Akhmatova's "Poem Without a Hero."

There's also debate about the exact time period that defines the "Silver Age." Its beginning is generally placed around the 1890s, with the publication of Merezhkovsky's collections and the poetry of Zinaida Gippius and Konstantin Balmont.

There is disagreement over the dates of its completion: some researchers point to the October Revolution and the beginning of the Civil War, others to 1921 – the year of Blok's death and Gumilev's execution; the year of Mayakovsky's suicide is also mentioned.

Many poets and writers of the Silver Age survived the change of eras and continued to publish after the 1930s, publishing critical articles and memoirs while in exile.

The Silver Age marked a new stage of development not only in literature, but also in painting, music, theater, and ballet. This was a time of modernism: experiments with symbolism, content, and poetic form, and the search for new means of expression.

The poets of the Silver Age sought to renew language and imagery, to go beyond traditional canons.

A deep interest in philosophical and metaphysical questions: unlike the literature of the previous period, the emphasis was not on topical social problems, but on global questions of existence, the meaning of life, death, and love.

Mysticism and irrationality: many poets explored mysticism, religious themes, and were interested in the occult, dreams, and premonitions.

Use of symbols and allegories: Symbolism became one of the key artistic devices for conveying the polysemy and ambiguity of the world.

Musicality and sound design of poetry: Particular attention was paid to the melody and rhythm of poetry, as well as its musical organization.

Development of literary movements and schools: During this period, various poetic associations with their own manifestos and aesthetic programs actively formed and interacted.

Silver Age Movements:

Symbolism

A new literary movement, Symbolism, was born out of the profound crisis that gripped European culture at the end of the 19th century. This crisis manifested itself in a negative assessment of progressive social ideas, a reconsideration of moral values, a loss of faith in the power of scientific consciousness, and a fascination with idealistic philosophy. Russian Symbolism arose in the years of the collapse of populism and the widespread spread of pessimism. All this led to the fact that the literature of the Silver Age raised not pressing social issues, but global philosophical ones. The chronological framework of Russian Symbolism is the 1890s–1910. Two literary traditions influenced the development of Symbolism in Russia:

The Russian poetry of Fet and Tyutchev, the prose of Dostoevsky.

French Symbolism—the poetry of Paul Verlaine, Arthur Rimbaud, and Charles Baudelaire. The central idea is that art is a means of understanding the world.

Symbolism was not homogeneous. It had distinct schools and movements (for example, the "senior" and "junior" Symbolists).

"Elder" Symbolists

The "elder" Symbolists include:

St. Petersburg writers D.S. Merezhkovsky, Z.N. Gippius, F.K. Sologub, and N.M. Minsky. The work of the St. Petersburg Symbolists was initially dominated by a decadent mood and motifs of disillusionment. Therefore, their work is sometimes called "decadent."

Moscow poets V. Ya. Bryusov and K. D. Balmont.

The "older" Symbolists perceived Symbolism in aesthetic terms. According to Bryusov and Balmont, a poet is, above all, a creator of purely personal and purely artistic values.

The "younger" Symbolists (younger Symbolists): these include A. A. Blok, Bely, and V. I. Ivanov. The "younger" Symbolists perceived Symbolism in a philosophical and religious vein. For them, Symbolism was philosophy refracted through poetic consciousness.

Color symbolism is used. A. Bely, in his article "Sacred Colors" (1905), explains the meaning of certain colors: white – goodness, harmony (hence his pseudonym); black – evil, chaos; gray – the presence of evil, chaos, and the devil in everyday life; red – love, passion, suffering, etc.

The image-symbol is polysemantic, often its meanings are only vaguely felt, they cannot be fully expressed in a precise word or concept.

For example, "You" in A. Blok's poems is a beloved girl, spring, the Beautiful Lady, the Princess, Eternal Femininity, and the Motherland. The symbols of dawn, sunrise, stars, fog, ships, wind, and snowstorm are all polysemantic.

Symbolist poets made a significant contribution to the development of Russian culture. The most talented of them, in their own way, captured the tragic plight of individuals unable to find their place in life, in a world shaken by monumental social conflicts, and sought new ways to artistically understand the world. They made significant discoveries in the fields of poetics, the rhythm of verse, and the enhancement of its musical element.

Acmeism

Acmeism was born as a protest against Symbolism. Acmeism's founder, Nikolai Gumilev, restored clarity of imagery, references to ancient times, simplicity of language, and a love of life to poetry.

Sensing a crisis in Symbolism, in 1911, Gumilev, together with Sergei Gorodetsky, founded the poetic association "The Guild of Poets." Acmeist poets returned to the naturalness of the material world and primordial feelings, while the Symbolists were perceived as "tragic dreamers."

The Acmeists offered nothing new—they restored poets' ability to freely use the means of language. For them, "this was a yearning for world culture." They sought to find poetry in the mundane details of life.

The Acmeists called for poetry to be purged of philosophy and all sorts of symbols, proclaiming a return to the material world and accepting it as it is: with its joys and vices, evil and injustice, asserted the principle of "art for art's sake."

In the context of the revolutionary upsurge and the crisis of autocracy, Acmeism and Futurism proved unviable and ceased to exist by the end of the 1910 s.

Imagism

Imagism (from the French and English "image") is a literary and artistic movement that emerged in Russia in the first post-revolutionary years based on the literary practice of Futurism.

The main characteristics of Imagism:

- the primacy of the "image as such"; image is the most general category, replacing the evaluative concept of artistry;
- poetic creativity is a process of language development through metaphor;
- an epithet is the sum of metaphors, comparisons, and contrasts of some object;
- poetic content is the evolution of image and epithet as the most primitive image;

The Imagists declared that the purpose of creativity is the creation of an image.

The Imagists' primary means of expression is metaphor, often metaphorical chains that juxtapose various elements of two images: literal and figurative. The Imagists' creative practice is characterized by shock value and anarchic motifs. The style and general behavior of Imagism were influenced by Russian Futurism.

The founders of Imagism were Anatoly Mariengof, Vadim Shershenevich, and Sergei Yesenin.

Imagism was the last prominent school of Russian poetry in the 20th century. This movement was founded two years after the Revolution, but its substantive focus had nothing in common with the Revolution.

Beyond the Movements

Among the representatives of the Silver Age were those who did not belong to any of the movements listed above. Besides the main movements and poetic associations, there were authors who wrote satirical and proletarian poetry, constructivists, and OBERIUs (a movement of real art).

These include Ivan Bunin, Vladislav Khodasevich, Marina Tsvetaeva, Daniil Kharms and Boris Pasternak, who created their works outside the literary canon.

What was most notable and defining about the artistic form of Silver Age literature, especially its poetry?

What are the main lessons of the Silver Age, its strengths and weaknesses, its discoveries and its mistakes?

This is a century of unprecedented grace and beauty in the Russian language, especially in poetry. Blok and Bely, Tsvetaeva and Mayakovsky, Akhmatova and Gumilev, Yesenin and Klyuyev, and many other names of first-class poets—these are the names that will remain in Russian memory, and that is beyond dispute.

Russian poetry of the Silver Age traveled a long way in a very short time.

It sowed its seeds into the future. The thread of legends and traditions has not been broken. Turn-of-the-century poetry is a complex cultural phenomenon, interest in which is only just beginning to awaken. More and more discoveries await us.

The poetry of the "Silver Age" reflected, in its large and small magical mirrors, the complex and ambiguous process of Russia's socio-political, spiritual, moral, aesthetic, and cultural development during a period marked by three revolutions, a world war, and an especially terrible internal civil war.

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What is the essence of the "Silver Age" phenomenon in Russian poetry? What makes this phenomenon unified? Despite the diversity of movements and creative individuals, this poetry expressed the worldview of a single era—an era a turning point, a crisis, a breakthrough. This explains the acute sense, common to all the poets of the "Silver Age," of an individual experiencing a dramatic moment of disillusionment with previous forms of life and seeking a way to a new harmony with the world. Each poet interpreted the relationship between man and time in his own way, striving to overcome their antagonism. The poetry of the "Silver Age"

"The Silver Age" is imbued with a sense of each individual's inseparable connection to the shared destiny of

Russia. While imagining the future of the Motherland differently, the poets agree on key points: humanism, the idea of a free creative individual.

The key significance of the literature of the Silver Age is the flourishing of poetry and the diversity of movements:

- The era gave birth to many new directions, opposing and complementing each other: symbolism (the search for hidden meanings), acmeism (a return to clarity of image), futurism (experiments with language).

- Paradigm shift: a transition from 19th-century realism to a modernist worldview, where attention shifts from social issues to the individual's inner world, their emotional experiences, and philosophical quests.

"Golden Names": the era produced a constellation of outstanding authors: Blok, Akhmatova, Gumilev, Mandelstam, Tsvetaeva, Pasternak, Yesenin, Bryusov, Balmont, Gippius, and others.

- Synthesis of the arts: literature was closely intertwined with philosophy, theater, music, and painting, creating a unified cultural space. This period saw the "awakening" of independent philosophical thought

and a heightened aesthetic sensibility, a response to the crisis of consciousness at the turn of the century.

Some scholars believe the Silver Age ended with the outbreak of the Civil War. Others believe it ended with the death of Alexander Blok and the execution of Nikolai Gumilyov. Another view is that the end of the Silver Age can be considered to have occurred in the late 1920s and early 1930s.

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